

Gifted Plants and Artistic Patronage in Early Modern Japan

Tan'yū's Sketches of Flowers and Plants

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Introduction

The five-volume *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* (Tokyo National Museum, A-216; hereafter "Tokyo National Museum version") and the one-volume *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* included in *Tan'yū Shukuzu* (Kyoto National Museum, A 甲-242-3; hereafter "Kyoto National Museum version") are botanical sketches by Kanō Tan'yū (1602–1674), one of the leading painters of the 17th century. Based on inscriptions found within these works, they are believed to have been produced between 1661 (Manji 4 / Kanbun 1) and 1674 (Enpō 2). Aside from these two extant examples, very few sketches by Tan'yū have been identified, suggesting that the surviving works are limited to his later years.

However, the fact that the extant works are from Tan'yū's later years does not necessarily mean that he engaged in sketching exclusively during that period. Tan'yū's residence was destroyed in the Great Fire of Meireki,² which likely resulted in the loss of many of his preliminary drawings and sketches. Therefore, analyzing Tan'yū's perspective on sketching solely based on the surviving works from 1661 onward may be problematic. If one were to examine the extant sketches, it would be necessary to consider not only Tan'yū's artistic activities in his later years but also the rise of horticultural culture and natural history during that period.

At the time, Tan'yū's nephew, Kano Tsunenobu (1636–1713), actively engaged in sketching and left behind a substantial body of work, including the 29-volume *Sketches of Flowers, Fish, Shellfish, and Insects* (Tokyo National Museum, A-4555). Many retainers of the Tokugawa shogunate were involved in these sketches, reflecting a high level of interest in the structure and ecology of the depicted subjects. This interest can even be seen as a precursor to the flourishing of natural history studies during the

Kyōhō era (1716–1736) and beyond.³ Moreover, among *Tsunenobu’s sketches*, which he began in the same year as Tan’yū’s works—1661 (Manji 4/Kanbun 1)—there exists a piece titled *Yomega Kobukuro*, which was drawn at the same location and on the same day as *Tan’yū’s sketches*. This suggests the possibility of a collaborative effort between Tan’yū and Tsunenobu.⁴ The characteristics of *Tsunenobu’s sketches* have already been examined in detail by Naohide Isono,⁵ and it has been suggested that Tsunenobu may have undertaken these sketches as part of official shogunate duties, based on the providers of the depicted subjects.⁶

In contrast, Tan’yū’s sketches are generally considered to have been created as preparatory studies for finished paintings, rather than from an interest in materia medica or natural history.⁷ Nevertheless, there are common elements between Tan’yū and Tsunenobu, and examining these similarities and differences is a key aspect of this study. This paper, therefore, aims to analyze the background of Tan’yū’s sketches by considering his activities from the Manji era onward, as well as information about those who provided the depicted subjects, in order to explore the context in which these works were created. Extensive prior research has already been conducted on the Tokyo and Kyoto National Museum versions of *Sketches of Flowers and Plants*,⁸ and full reproductions with annotations have been published.⁹ This study will build upon these existing findings, while primarily focusing on the dated sketches to offer further insights.

I. Trends in Tan’yū’s Sketch Production

To begin, this study extracts the dated sketches from the Tokyo National Museum and Kyoto National Museum versions, arranges them in chronological order, and examines trends in their production. When examined chronologically, it becomes evident that Tan’yū’s sketching continued without interruption until his final years. A notable concentration of works appears between 1661 (Kanbun 1) and 1665 (Kanbun 5). While most of the sketches are undated—making it difficult to conclude definitively that they were produced during this period—this cluster serves as a significant point of reference. After 1666—or more precisely, from 1667 onward, as no dated examples exist for 1666—sketch production appears to continue sporadically. Nevertheless, even based

solely on the dated works, it is reasonable to infer that Tan'yū engaged in sketching with particular intensity between 1661 and 1665.

When compared with Tsunenobu's sketching activity,¹⁰ a striking contrast emerges. Between 1661 and 1665, only three of Tsunenobu's sketches are extant. However, from 1666 onward, the number increases dramatically: ten dated sketches survive from that year alone, twenty-three in the following year, and approximately ten sketches annually continue into his later years. Was this shift in the patterns of sketch production between Tan'yū and Tsunenobu merely coincidental? Considering the overall trend, it seems plausible that specific factors motivated Tan'yū's intensive sketching activity between 1661 and 1666, as well as Tsunenobu's increasing engagement in sketching from 1666 onward.

Next, this section examines the relationship between the production of *Tan'yū's sketches* and his finished paintings. As mentioned above, the most appropriate comparative material would be works from the same period—namely, from the Manji era onward. The following four works will be considered:

1. *Kaidō ni Onagadori-zu* (Museum of Fine Arts, Boston)
– Based on its signature and seals, this work is dated to the Manji era (hereafter referred to as the "Boston Museum version").
2. *Hikin Sōjū-zu Kan* (Tokyo National Museum, A-1075)
– Dated to 1666 (Kanbun 6).
3. *Kaidō ni Onagadori-zu* (Tokyo National Museum, A-252)
– Dated to 1670 (Kanbun 10).
4. *Shiki Kachō-zu* (Eiheiji)
– Dated to 1672 (Kanbun 12), based on the inscription "aged 71 years" (by East Asian age reckoning).

Additionally, another work depicting trees and birds, *Shōkaku, Chikkaku, Jurōjin-zu* (Fukuoka Art Museum, Kanbun 7), will also be included in this analysis. Through these works, I will examine the relationship between Tan'yū's bird-and-flower paintings and his sketches. First, the *Shiki Kachō-zu* housed at Eiheiji (hereafter referred to as the "Eiheiji version") consists of a set of four hanging scrolls depicting various plants and numerous birds (Plate 1). The inscription states "aged 71 years," which corresponds to 70 years old in modern terms, based on East Asian age reckoning. This indicates that the work was created in 1672 (Kanbun 12), the year of Tan'yū's seventieth birthday, during

a period when he was reportedly suffering from a stroke.¹¹ Analyzing the trends in his sketches, it is evident that he had been actively engaged in live sketching up until 1672. This suggests that for Tan'yū, direct observational sketching was a well-established practice that allowed him to depict subjects with remarkable accuracy. However, does the Eiheiji version reflect any influence from his sketches?

In the spring panel, plum trees and peonies are depicted, along with a composition centered on a golden pheasant, accompanied by a Korean nightingale, a Japanese accentor, a bullfinch, a sparrow, a narcissus flycatcher, and a white wagtail. The summer panel features an egret as its focal point, surrounded by a swallow, a scarlet minivet, a kingfisher, and a meadow bunting. The autumn panel presents a composition of maple trees and hibiscus, where a silver pheasant serves as the central figure, accompanied by a departing wild goose, a blue magpie, a varied tit, a quail, a woodcock, a wren, and a Japanese accentor. The winter panel incorporates pines, camellias, and reeds, with a red-crowned crane as the primary subject, along with a duck, a mandarin duck, a long-tailed tit, a green pigeon, a fairy bluebird, a common myna, a great tit, and a great spotted woodpecker. As evidenced by these elaborate compositions, the Eiheiji version is abundant in floral and avian motifs, making it a significant example for analyzing Tan'yū's *kachō* (bird-and-flower) depictions.¹² If sketching influences the creation of finished paintings, such an effect should first be observable in the accuracy of proportions and balance in the motifs. Furthermore, in the detailed rendering of motifs, distinctive features of the depicted subjects should be faithfully recorded. For instance, in botanical illustrations, elements such as the number of stamens, petals, and leaf veins should be captured, whereas in avian depictions, attributes like the number of feathers should be represented. Previous studies have acknowledged this notion, and discussions regarding the relationship between finished paintings and sketch drawings have primarily focused on proportion and detailed rendering.¹³

Let us now examine the Eiheiji version. In its depiction of trees, no influence of sketching is discernible, as the rendering adheres to the stylistic conventions of the Kanō school (Figure 1). In the portrayal of flowers, including peonies, hibiscus, and camellias, frontality is emphasized over precise proportions (Figure 2). Thus, in the Eiheiji version, produced in the twelfth year of the Kabun era (1672), the influence of sketch drawings appears to be minimal. This observation supports the prevailing view that Tan'yū maintained a strict distinction between finished paintings and sketch drawings. Instead, the Eiheiji version can be seen as a work that reflects Tan'yū's

absorption of *kachō* painting traditions, particularly those found in quadriptych compositions, such as "Bird-and-Flower Paintings of the Four Seasons" by Lü Ji (Tokyo National Museum, TA-44). A particularly noteworthy aspect is Tan'yū's adaptation of duck motifs from one of the bird-and-flower paintings attributed to Sesshū, specifically the "Bird-and-Flower Folding Screen of the Four Seasons" housed in the Asian Art Museum of San Francisco (Figures 3 and 4). Additionally, the depictions of peonies and Chinese peonies in the Eiheiji version exhibit close affinity with those in the San Francisco museum's work (Figures 5 and 6). Consequently, the Eiheiji version should be regarded as a *kachō* painting that prioritizes classical elements, while also serving as an example of Tan'yū's incorporation of compositional motifs from Sesshū-style bird-and-flower paintings.¹⁴

Figure 1: *Birds and Flowers of the Four Seasons* (detail), Eiheiji, 1672 (Kanbun 12)

Figure 2: Same

Figure 3: Same

Figure 4: *Birds and Flowers of the Four Seasons* (detail), the Asian Art Museum of San Francisco, 16th century

Figure 5: Same as Figure 1

Figure 6: Same as Figure 4

Meanwhile, there are also examples from this period where motifs were directly borrowed from sketch drawings. One such case is the "Pine and Crane" painting (Figure 7) from a triptych in the collection of the Fukuoka Art Museum. Focusing on the crane's legs (Figure 8), it is evident that the depiction of its toes adopts a motif from the sketch of a salt crane contained in the *Tan'yū Shukuzu* (探幽縮図, Tan'yū's reduced sketches) housed in the Kyoto National Museum (Figure 9).¹⁵ While the "Pine and Crane" painting from the Fukuoka Art Museum follows the "gu bu" (walking crane) and "shu ling" (preening crane) formats, which were among the six canonical crane postures (六鶴) adopted by the Kanō school,¹⁶ the depiction of the legs clearly shows an influence from sketching. This suggests that during the Kanbun era, Tan'yū exhibited an expressive fluctuation, moving between finished paintings and sketches. The following example further illustrates this fluctuation in expression.

Numerous works attributed to Tan'yū depict long-tailed birds, specifically blue magpies (mountain magpies). The extent of his preference for "long-tailed bird paintings" is evident in several monumental works, including the "Plum and Bamboo with Birds in Snow" (Kanei 11, 1634) in the Jorakuden Hall of Nagoya Castle, the aforementioned Eiheiji version (Example 4), and the "Handscroll of Birds and Beasts" (Example 2). Each of these features the delicate presence of the mountain magpie.¹⁷ Among them, the "Long-Tailed Bird and Chinese Quince" paintings from the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston (Example 1) and the Tokyo National Museum (Example 3) serve as prime examples. The depiction of the Chinese quince tree, on which the mountain magpie perches, is rendered with an accuracy so striking that it closely resembles the botanical sketch of "Chinese Quince" (Figure 10).

Figure 7: *Pine and Cranes*
the Fukuoka Art Museum
1667 (Kanbun 7)

Figure 8: *Same* (detail)

Figure 9: *Tan'yū Shukuzu*
Kyoto National Museum

Figure 10: *Sketches of Flowers and Plants, Spring Volume* (Chinese crabapple),
Tokyo National Museum, 17th century

Regarding the Boston Museum version, Jin Matsushima has already pointed out the influence of sketching in the depiction of the Chinese quince.¹⁸ Matsushima highlights that the mountain magpie as depicted by Tan'yū inherits imagery shared in East Asian bird-and-flower paintings, tracing back to the works of Bian Wenjin and Lü Ji. Additionally, he argues that the experience of sketching is evident in the depiction of the Chinese quince, particularly in the swift, precise strokes capturing its form and in the application of color, where blended tones and gradations effectively render the texture of the subject.

As Matsushima's study suggests, a close examination of the Boston Museum version (Example 1) and the Tokyo National Museum's *Kaidō ni Onagadori-zu* (Example 3) reveals a distinctive contrast. While the mountain magpie itself is depicted in a classical style imbued with spiritual significance, the branches of the Chinese quince tree on which it perches are executed with rapid, sketch-like brushstrokes. The unique white-to-red gradation of the flowers is applied with a loosely executed brush, recreating the delicate coloration characteristic of the Chinese quince blossoms. The white petals, achieved through the interplay between the primed silk's soft cream color and the matte texture of white pigment (gofun), give a translucent effect. Additionally, the subtle touches of vermilion deftly inserted throughout the composition beautifully replicate the delicate gradient of the Chinese quince's petals, enhancing the painting's visual elegance.

Tan'yū, while adhering to classical traditions, expanded the scope of his artistic expression by incorporating fresh images derived from his daily sketches. It is plausible that as he navigated between his formal paintings and sketch studies, he allowed these two modes of expression to resonate with each other, ultimately crystallizing into a single masterpiece, as exemplified by *Plum Blossoms and Long-tailed Birds*.

Meanwhile, when considering Tan'yū's sketch-based representations, the *Otter* (獺 図) in the collection of the Fukuoka Art Museum presents a particularly challenging case in terms of its placement within his oeuvre. A comparative examination of the Tokyo National Museum's *Kaidō ni Onagadori-zu* (Example 3), the Eiheiiji version (Example 4), the Fukuoka Art Museum version (Example 5), and the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston version (Example 1) suggests that Tan'yū alternated between prioritizing classical conventions and integrating novel imagery derived from direct observation. However, the motivation for creating a work like *Otter*—a piece primarily informed by the visual language of sketching, distinguished by its accurate proportions and

naturalistic color palette—warrants further investigation. In pursuing this question, it is essential to consider other sketch-based examples, including the Tokyo National Museum and Kyoto National Museum versions. The immediacy and direct observational qualities evident in these works suggest that their creation may have been closely tied to the specific contextual circumstances under which they were produced. Thus, in the following discussion, I will explore the individuals involved in the creation of these sketches as an entry point for examining the background of their production.

II. Providers of Subjects for Sketch Studies and Their Networks

To gain insight into the background of *Tan'yū's sketch* studies, I will first enumerate the individuals and institutions that provided him with plant specimens.

Among the annotations, several temples are mentioned by name or by their temple titles, including Jakōin (寂光院), Konchi-in (金地院), and Un'yasu-in (雲益院). Of these, the only documented interaction with Tan'yū, based on the available evidence, is with Konchi-in. At the time, the temple was under the third-generation abbot Chikuin Sōgo (竺隱崇五). It goes without saying that Tan'yū had a deep friendship with the first-generation abbot Ishin Sūden (以心崇伝). However, it is notable that Tan'yū maintained relations with Konchi-in even after the first generation, and that these exchanges included the gifting of plants. On February 19 of an unspecified year, Konchi-in presented him with forsythia (*rengedō*), and on April 8 of Kanbun 2 (1662), he received a magnolia (Figure 11). Given the large, sprawling branches of the magnolia, it is possible that Tan'yū sketched it on-site during a visit to Konchi-in.

Figure 11: *Sketches of Flowers and Plants, Summer Volume* (Magnolia), Tokyo National Museum, 17th century

Regarding Jakōin, little is known.¹⁹ As for Un'yasu-in, it is likely the renowned temple in Kanagawa mentioned in *Shinpen Musashi Fudoki-kō* (『新編武蔵風土記稿』), which records that "on June 8 of Keichō 4 (1599), Tōshōgū granted the temple a stipend of 20 koku of land." While Tan'yū's association with this temple remains unclear, it is documented that on March 11 of an unspecified year, a camellia was gifted to him, which he then depicted in a painting.

Among the three Tokugawa branch families, the Kii branch is represented by Tokugawa Mitsusada (1627–1705), who is referred to as "Kishū-sama" (紀州様). Mitsusada, the father of Shōgun Yoshimune (吉宗), was an accomplished ink painter and a student of Tan'yū.²⁰ On March 19 of Kanbun 13 (1673), Tan'yū painted a white peony gifted to him by Mitsusada, accompanied by the inscription "uchinuki, keshimi to iunari" (うちぬき、けしμιと言也), though the exact meaning of this phrase remains unclear.

Among feudal lords and shogunate retainers, there is Tōdō Izumi-no-kami, known as Tōdō Takahisa (1638–1703). Takahisa was the grandson of Tōdō Takatora and the third daimyō of the Tsu Domain in Ise Province. According to *Kansei Chōshū Shokafu* (『寛政重修諸家譜』), he had his first audience with Shōgun Iemitsu in Shōhō 1 (1644), and in Jōō 3 (1654), he was granted the court rank of *Jushii-ge* (従四位下) and the title of Governor of Izumi. In July of an unspecified year, Tan'yū inscribed a note stating, "This flower, known as *kusabotan* (草牡丹), is from Tōdō Izumi-no-kami," and painted what is now identified as *Clematis stans*.

Similarly, Hosokawa Etchū-no-kami, or Hosokawa Tsunatoshi (1635–1714), was a descendant of Hosokawa Yūsai and the third daimyō of the Kumamoto Domain in Higo Province. According to *Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, he had his first audience with Shōgun Iemitsu in Shōhō 2 (1645), and in Keian 3 (1650), at the age of six, he inherited his father Mitsunao's domain. In Jōō 2 (1653), he underwent the *genpuku* (元服) coming-of-age ceremony in the presence of Shōgun Ietsuna and was granted the court rank of *Jushii-ge* and the title of Governor of Etchū. In Kanbun 11 (1671), he compiled the collected works of Hosokawa Yūsai and entrusted them to Asukai Masakuni, receiving an imperial title from Emperor Go-Mizunoo, who named the collection *Shumyōshū* (『衆妙集』). On July 19 of an unspecified year, Tan'yū inscribed a note stating, "From the residence of Hosokawa Etchū-no-kami" and painted a *kinmizuhiki* (*Agrimonia*).

Additionally, Abe Bungo-no-kami, or Abe Tada'aki (1602–1675), was the lord of Mibu Domain in Shimotsuke Province and later the lord of Oshi Domain in Musashi Province. According to *Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, in Kan'ei 1 (1624), he inherited his father's domain of 6,000 koku, received an additional 10,000 koku in Kan'ei 3 (1626), and was appointed as a *koshōgashira* (小姓頭) in the service of Shōgun Iemitsu. In Kan'ei 10 (1633), he was promoted to the *Rokuninshū* (六人衆) and later to the position of *Rōjū-kaku* (老中格). On April 2 of Kanbun 9 (1669), Tan'yū painted a columbine (*odamaki*) gifted to him by Tada'aki (Figure 12).

Figure 12: *Sketches of Flowers and Plants, Summer Volume* (Columbine), Tokyo National Museum, 17th century

Kurihara Jin'emon, or Kurihara Toshizane (d. 1684), was a retainer of the shogunate. According to *Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, in Kan'ei 19 (1642), he succeeded his father, Kurihara Toshitomo (d. 1641), who had served as a *konando-ban* (小納戸番), and later held a position in the *ōban* (大番). He passed away in Jōkyō 1 (1684). The Kurihara family held successive positions as *konando-ban* and *ōban* officials within the shogunate. On May 11 of Kanbun 2 (1662), Tan'yū painted a *ko-aoi* (*Zeniaoi*, *Malva*), on September 19 of Kanbun 5 (1665), a *sanshō-giku* (*Ogura-giku*, *Chrysanthemum*), and on an unspecified date, a *sukashi-yuri* (*Lilium maculatum*).

Lastly, "Kitami Kyūdaiyū" refers to Kitami Shigekatsu (1604–1685). According to *Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Shigekatsu served as a *metsuke* (目付, inspector) and later as an *Ōsaka metsuke*. He was also highly skilled in the art of the tea ceremony and became the founder of the Kitami school (喜多見流). Although the exact year is uncertain, on the last day of August, he presented Tan'yū with a rare taro flower (*satoimo no hana*),

which Tan'yū painted, annotating it with the note: "*The flower is indeed yellow—Egui-mo no hana*" (Figure 13).

The above is a compilation of individuals mentioned in the annotations. In addition to those listed, many other figures appear whose details remain unclear. Further investigation into these individuals remains a subject for future research.²¹

Figure 13: *Sketches of Flowers and Plants, Autumn Volume* (Taro), Tokyo National Museum, Edo period, 17th century

III. Individuals Surrounding Tan'yū—Masanori Inaba and the Dutch Trading Post

In the previous chapter, Kitami Shigekatsu was identified as one of the individuals who provided subjects for *Tan'yū's sketches*. Given Shigekatsu's mastery of the tea ceremony and Tan'yū's status as an *oku eshi* (奥絵師, official painter of the Tokugawa shogunate), it is easy to imagine that their relationship extended beyond official commissions into the realm of refined artistic and cultural exchange. A document that provides concrete evidence of this deeper connection is the *Eidai Nikki* (『永代日記』), found in the *Yodo Inaba-ke Monjo* (『淀稲葉家文書』).²²

The *Eidai Nikki* was compiled under the orders of Inaba Masanori (1623–1696), lord of the Odawara Domain in Sagami Province. A grandson of Kasuga no Tsubone (春日局), Masanori was one of the most influential figures in the Tokugawa

administration and played a central role in managing trade relations with the Dutch trading post at Nagasaki. In his study on *bakufu* (幕府) ministers and hereditary retainers, Shimoju Kiyoshi lists the visitors to the Inaba household in Kanbun 1 (1661).²³ This record shows that in that year alone, Kitami Shigekatsu visited the Inaba residence six times, while Tan'yū visited five times. That same year, a marriage took place between the Hosokawa and Inaba families, likely necessitating artistic commissions related to the wedding celebrations. The *Eidai Nikki* thus offers a glimpse into Tan'yū's deepening ties with Masanori and Shigekatsu. This suggests that Shigekatsu, who had gifted Tan'yū a rare taro flower, was more than just a casual acquaintance; he was part of an intimate social circle that gathered at the Inaba household.

Examining the relationship between Masanori Inaba and Tan'yū through the lens of "sketch studies" leads to an intriguing connection with a particular book—Dodonaeus's *Cruydeboeck* (『草木譜』). In Manji 2 (1659), or possibly the previous year, the Dutch trading post gifted *Cruydeboeck* to Masanori, then known as Inaba Mino-no-kami. However, Masanori returned the book, citing the reason that "the print was too small".²⁴ The *Cruydeboeck* was an oversized book, measuring over 41 cm in height. The complaint about the "small print" likely referred to the illustrations rather than the text. Furthermore, Masanori reportedly requested "a larger, more beautifully illustrated version" in its place. It is remarkable that he evaluated *Cruydeboeck* from an aesthetic standpoint rather than as a work of pharmacology or natural history. Given his personal connection with Tan'yū, it is plausible that he shared *Cruydeboeck* with him. Could Masanori's request for "larger, more beautifully illustrated images" have been prompted by a comment from Tan'yū? If so, Tan'yū may have examined *Cruydeboeck* with astonishment and wished to see more Western botanical illustrations on a grander scale.

A comparison between the carnation illustration in *Cruydeboeck* (Figure 14) and Tan'yū's depiction of *Oranda-nadeshiko* (オランダナデシコ, "Dutch pink") (Figure 15) is particularly illuminating. Rather than depicting the entire plant, Tan'yū arranged the cuttings in a horizontal row, meticulously capturing the details of the stamens, petals, and leaf structure with extraordinary accuracy. The resemblance between the two illustrations suggests a striking visual correspondence.

Notably, Tan'yū visited the Dutch trading post multiple times in his later years and even received a medical consultation from a Dutch physician in Kanbun 10 (1670).²⁵

Given these interactions, it is not difficult to imagine that Tan’yū had access to the latest Western knowledge through the Dutch. It is also significant that Tan’yū’s surviving sketch studies date from Manji 4 (1661), shortly after *Cruydeboeck* was imported into Japan. That same year, his nephew Tsuneshige (常信), then in his twenties, also began sketching from life. Based on the example of *Yome ga Kobukuro* (よめが小袋), it has been suggested that Tan’yū acted as the master while Tsuneshige served as his assistant.²⁶ If this was indeed the case, it follows that Tan’yū, having been inspired by Western botanical illustrations, passed on the practice of sketch studies to Tsuneshige, marking a significant transition around Kanbun 6 (1666).

Figure 14: *Cruydeboeck* by Rembert Dodoens, Tokyo National Museum, 17th century

Figure 15: *Sketches of Flowers and Plants, Autumn Volume* (Dutch pink), Tokyo National Museum, 17th century

Conclusion

This study has examined Tan’yū’s artistic trajectory by tracing chronological markers in his works. If we consider the period from Kanbun 1 to Kanbun 5 (1661–1665) as the

peak of his sketch study production, the fact that he continued to produce an extensive number of reduced copies of classical paintings throughout his later years suggests that he may have gradually scaled back his sketch work after this period, entrusting the practice to his nephew, Tsuneshige.

Tan'yū's sketches capture the pure beauty of nature as it exists, while Tsuneshige's works reveal a keen interest in biological structures. Both artists may have engaged in sketching within the broader intellectual context of the Edo period, drawing upon the traditional study of *honzōgaku* (herbal studies), which was gaining traction within the shogunate, as well as the emerging body of knowledge from *rangaku* (蘭学, Dutch studies). It is only natural that figures such as Inaba Masanori and other high-ranking retainers played a role in fostering this artistic and scientific inquiry.

Tan'yū was not only an *oku eshi* (official painter of the shogunate) but also a prominent cultural figure who maintained close relationships with shogunate officials and the court nobility. He had access to the most cutting-edge intellectual spheres of his time, engaging with the most refined domains of knowledge. Within this trajectory, the young Tsuneshige inherited the tradition of sketch studies as a form of intellectual inquiry, ultimately producing a vast body of work.

Tan'yū's sketch studies testify to his exceptional status as a pioneering artist, even in his later years. At the same time, they serve as invaluable records of Edo-period perspectives on nature, offering a glimpse into the ways in which the natural world was observed and interpreted in early modern Japan.

Notes

1. Several sketch studies are included in *Tan'yū Shukuzu* (探幽縮図), which is now dispersed across multiple collections. For example, among the *Tan'yū Shukuzu* housed at the Kyoto National Museum, the *Hawk Scroll* (鷹図巻) includes a sketch of a salt crane (塩鶴) dated to Kanbun 7 (1667). Given its connection to the falconry system, this salt crane sketch was likely created as an official commission.
2. According to *Tokugawa Jikki* (『徳川実紀』) and *Kakumeiki*, Tan'yū's residence was destroyed in the great fire of Meireki 2 (1656), in October.

3. Mayumi Ono, "The Background of the Creation of *Kano Tsunenobu's Sketch Scroll of Flowers, Fish, Shellfish, and Insects*: Trends in the Chronological Order of Sketches and Providers of Subject Matter," *Bulletin of the Tokyo National Museum*, vol. 49, 2014.
4. Naohide Isono, "Kusabana Gyokai Chūruī Shaseizu as a Source of Natural History," *MUSEUM*, no. 590, 2004.
5. Ibid. (Note 4), pp. 9–28.
6. Ibid. (Note 3), pp. 135–156.
7. Riko Imahashi, *The Flower Perceived by the Mind: Konoe Iehiro's Shinka Mokushō and Kaiki (Edo no Kachōga: Hakubutsugaku o Meguru Bunka to Sono Hyōshō)*, Skydore, 1995, and Note 3, pp. 157–159. Additionally, many scholars argue that *Tan'yū's sketches* were not preparatory studies for formal paintings but rather purely observational studies.
8. Tanio Nakamura and Shirō Kitamura, *Kano Tan'yū's Botanical Sketches in the Collection of the Tokyo National Museum*, Shikōsha, 1977.
9. However, in the book cited in Note 8, the *Spring Volume* lacks the second sheet. In the *Summer Volume* and *Autumn Volume*, the pages currently positioned at the end are printed at the beginning, causing an inversion of orientation. Despite this, pages 35–53, 75–107, 113, and 121 are presented in their correct order. Additionally, in the *Summer Volume*, sheets 12–15, 24, and 25, as well as in the *Autumn Volume*, sheets 10, 19, and 21, are omitted. In the *Miscellaneous Volume 1*, sheets 1, 4, and 11 are missing, and in *Miscellaneous Volume 2*, sheets 1 and 15–20 are omitted, with only the lower row of sheets 4 and 10 missing.
10. Ibid. (Note 3), pp. 112–134.
11. Satoru Sakakibara, *Kano Tan'yū: The Portrait of an Official Painter*, Rinsen Shoten, 2014, pp. 425–427.
12. Tadashi Kobayashi and Yasushi Murashige, *The World of Kachōga V: Elegant Decorative Beauty—Early Edo Kachōga*, Gakushū Kenkyūsha, 1981, p. 156.
13. Yoshiya Yamashita, "Kano Tan'yū's Otter Painting and Kuroda Tadayuki" (*Exhibition Catalog: Kano School and Fukuoka*, Fukuoka City Art Museum, 1998); idem, "Kano Tan'yū and Bird Sketches—From the Newly Acquired *White Pheasant*," *Amaryllis*, no. 78, 2005; Hiroko Kato, "Noda Dōmin's *Bird Sketches* and its Relationship to Ogata Kōrin's *Bird and Animal Sketches*," *Bijutsushi* (Journal of Art History), no. 162, 2007; idem, "Kano Tan'yū's Theory of Sketching—Focusing on Birds, Animals, and Human Figures," *Kokka*, no. 1386, 2011.
14. Junji Nakajima, "The Formation of the Attributed Sesshū *Four Seasons Flower and Bird Folding Screens*," *Kokka*, no. 1422, 2014, pp. 7–8.

15. Mayumi Ono, "A Study on *Hawk and Crane* in Early Edo Period Paintings of Raptors— Focusing on the *Salt Crane Screens*," *MUSEUM*, no. 638, 2012, pp. 53–55.
16. Hiromitsu Ogawa, "The *Six Cranes* Wall Painting by Huang Quan and its Legacy (Part 2)," *Kokka*, no. 1297, 2003, pp. 7–8.
17. Ibid. (Note 11), pp. 206–207.
18. Jin Matsushima, "Kano Tan'yū's *Crabapple and Long-tailed Birds*," *Kokka*, no. 1428, 2014, pp. 29–34.
19. *Jakō-in* (寂光院) is likely the famous temple in Ōhara. *Jakō-in* houses the *Ōhara Gyōgyō Emaki*, which exhibits stylistic features of the Keichō-period Kano school.
20. *Nanki Tokugawa-shi*, vol. 1, Nanki Tokugawa-shi Kankōkai, 1930.
21. Among the figures noted in the annotations as providers of subject matter are Shinsei (信齊), Tōden (藤伝), Moribe Shōroku (森部庄六), Ōtosuke-dayū (大都助太夫), Enzui (園随), Sakai Ryōan (坂井了庵), Shibata Sanzaemon (芝田三左エ門), Tomita Rokuemon (冨田六衛門), Yukeya Shichirōzaemon (ゆけや七郎左衛門), Teiryō Gettoku (庭了月徳), and Chikura Yasuyuki (千蔵安之). Further research on these individuals remains a topic for future study.
22. *Documents of the Yodo Inaba Family in Yamashiro Province* (山城国淀稻葉家中文書) (Held at Inaba Shrine, microfilm available at the National Institute of Japanese Literature); and Odawara City Archives, *Index of the Inaba Family Eidai Nikki Held at Inaba Shrine in Kyoto's Fushimi Ward*, 1995.
23. Kiyoshi Shimojū, *The Political Structure of the Bakufu Ministers and Fudai Domains*, Iwata Shoin, 2006, pp. 209–228; idem, *Inaba Masanori and His Era: The Formation of Edo Society*, Odawara Library 6, Yumekobo, 2002, p. 26.
24. Arnoldus Montanus, *Gedenkwaardige Gesantschappen der Oost-Indische Maatschappij*, trans. Wada Bankichi, *Montanus Nihon-shi*, Hinoe Publishing, 1925, p. 425.
25. Timon Screech (trans. Jin Matsushima), "Kano Tan'yū and the Dutch East India Company," *Kokka*, no. 1402, 2012.
26. Ibid. (Note 4), pp. 25–26.

Postscript

This article is based on the original publication: Mayumi ONO, "Sketches of Flowers and Plants by Kanō Tan'yū: Chronology and the Sources of Objects," *MUSEUM* No. 657, pp. 45–61, August 2015 (in Japanese). The monochrome illustrations in this article are reproduced from the original publication. The color illustrations are sourced from ColBase, National Institutes for Cultural Heritage, Japan. Available at: <https://colbase.nich.go.jp/>. This research was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 25370150.

Materials

List of Botanical Sketches with Dates

Included in the Scrolls "*Sketches of Flowers and Plants*" and "*Sketches of Flowers and Plants*"

[Legend]

From the *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* (Tokyo National Museum version) and the *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* (Kyoto National Museum version), only those sketches bearing dates have been excerpted and listed in the following order: the date inscribed in the painting, the name of the plant, and other notes. Supplementary information by the author of this paper is shown in parentheses (). The relevant scroll and position of the illustration are indicated in brackets []. The Kyoto version of the *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* is labeled as "Kyoto version." Illegible characters are indicated with □. Annotations have been transcribed based on Tanio Nakamura and Shirō Kitamura, *Kano Tan'yū: Sketches of Plants and Flowers* (Shikōsha, 1977) and Kyoto National Museum, *Tan'yū Shukuzu, Vol. 1* (Dōhōsha Publishing, 1980). Notes by the author of this paper are indicated in the margins.

Kanbun 1 (1661)

(Manji 4) March 11

Hikan-zakura (early-blooming cherry)

"Came from Un'yaku-in"

[Kyoto version, lower row, illustration 32]

May 15

Koume (small plum)

"□a mi□□, brought one branch of small plum"

[Miscellaneous Scroll II, lower row, illustration 41]

Intercalary August 11

(Unknown)

"Brought as a substitute for yamabuki from Daijō-ji"

[Kyoto version, lower row, illustration 10]

Kanbun 2 (1662)

February 25

(Peach)

"Received from Tōden; white flowers, with slight pink"

[Spring Scroll, upper row, illustration 11]

February 27

(Camellia)

"Received from Daito Sukedayū"

[Spring Scroll, lower row, illustration 14]

February 29

(*Kerria japonica*)

"Sketched at Ueno"

[Spring Scroll, lower row, illustration 11]

March 22

(*Calendula*)

[Kyoto version, upper row, illustration 5]

March 24

(Poppy)

[Miscellaneous Scroll I, upper row, illustration 37]

April 8

"Hō (Magnolia) tree, received from Konchi-in Temple" (text: "今地院与来" with erroneous kana indicated as is)

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration unspecified]

April 17

(Turk's-cap lily)

[Summer Scroll, upper row, illustration ?]

May 11

Ko-aoi (Wild mallow)

"Received from Kurihara Zinemon"

[Summer Scroll, upper row, illustration 8]

Kanbun 3 (1663)

February 27

(Sakura / Cherry blossom)

"All of them were like this."

[Spring Scroll, illustration 8]

March 7

Kaido (Chinese flowering crabapple)

"Received from Moribe Shōroku; red kaido."

[Spring Scroll, illustration 21]

Fourth Month (Lunar Calendar) 21st

Aoi (hollyhock)

"Leaf color slightly dark, six petals; white six (petals), came from Kamo."

[Miscellaneous Scroll II, lower row]

Fourth Month 21st

Katsura (*Cercidiphyllum japonicum*)

"Leaf color: two halves, six (Suō) red wrinkles; received from Kamo."

[Miscellaneous Scroll II, lower row]

July 4

Ibara (wild rose or briar)

"Received from Eiho."

[Miscellaneous Scroll I, upper row, illustration 26]

September 6 (sketched)

(Pomegranate)

[Miscellaneous Scroll II, upper row]

September 23

Ashi (reed)

"Some kind of reed; from Ise; □□□□ volume, □ appearance, □□; returned □."

[Autumn Scroll, upper row, illustration 21]

October 8

Botan (peony)

"Received from Shinsai; early-blooming winter peony; very beautiful crimson."

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 27]

Kanbun 4 (1664)

February 8

(Rose)

"Received from Jakkō-in"

[Spring Scroll, lower row, illustration 17]

March 20

(*Kerria japonica*)

"Located on a cliff along the Kurama road."

[Spring Scroll, lower row, illustration 15]

May 11

Sharan-sōshu (*Paeonia suffruticosa* hybrid?)

"Received from Yukeya Shichirōzaemon; white flowers, like this sharan."

[Miscellaneous Scroll I, lower row]

Intercalary May 13

Mojizuri (*Nejibana* / *Spiranthes sinensis*)

"Received from Yoshida; twisted like this up to the tip; all turned into flowers."

[Miscellaneous Scroll I, lower row]

June 17

Yamabuki (*Japanese butterbur*)

"Received from Jakkō-in Temple."

[Spring Scroll, illustration 10]

June 18

Oguruma (*Inula britannica*)

[Kyoto version, upper row, illustration 18]

June 26

Hirugao (*morning glory/dayflower*)

[Kyoto version, lower row, illustration 11]

July

Hasu (*lotus*)

"Water — Yakushi's lotus"

[Autumn Scroll, lower row, illustration 8]

July 9

Hagi (*bush clover*)

"Received from Tomita Rokuemon; this hagi has a lovely rich color; the back side of the flower is slightly pale, the front flower is truly beautiful, a shading in deep crimson."

[Miscellaneous Scroll I, lower row]

July 19

Dandotsu (*Canna lily*)

"Came from Shinsai"

[Kyoto version, illustration 24]

July 29

Aki-kaidō (*autumn crabapple*)

"Came from Shinsai"

[Kyoto version, upper row, illustration 4]

Kanbun 4 (1664)

July 20

Sawagikyō (*swamp bellflower*)

"Received from Tomita Rokuemon"

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 7]

August 4

Sawakikyō

"Said to be sawakikyō"

[Miscellaneous Scroll I, lower row]

Kanbun 5 (1665)

April 10

(*Turk's-cap lily*)

"Received from Kurihara Jinemon"

[Summer Scroll, upper row, illustration 5]

April 12

Shakuyaku (Chinese peony)

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 21]

April 25

(Rose)

[Kyoto version, upper row, illustration 16]

May 1

(Wild vetch / *Vicia sativa*?)

"□inuendo — from here the classification of grasses"

[Kyoto version, upper row, illustration 17]

May 13

(Dutch pink / *Dianthus barbatus*)

[Autumn Scroll, lower row, illustration 34]

August 24

Ominaeshi (Golden lace)

"The color of the flower is truly beautiful and noble; after blooming, it lasts for five days."

[Autumn Scroll, upper row, illustration 26]

August 24

Soba no hana (buckwheat flower)

[Autumn Scroll, lower row, illustration 13]

August 24

(Bellflower gentian / *Adenophora triphylla*)

[Autumn Scroll, lower row, illustration 11]

September 19

Sanshōgiku (*Chrysanthemum* with pepper scent?)

"Received from Kurihara Jinemon"

[Autumn Scroll, lower row, illustration 29]

Kanbun 7 (1667)

March 7

Nanae□ (Seven-layered something)

(*Kurin-sō* / *Primula japonica*)

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 11]

Kanbun 8 (1668)

July 10

Kara-uri (Oriental gourd)

"Received from Teiryō Gettoku; as the karuri had started to grow, he asked me to sketch it."

[Miscellaneous Scroll II, upper row]

July 12

Kara-nasubi (Tomato)

"Tree height about four shaku (approx. 120 cm), no vines; upright plant. Received from Teiryō Gettoku. Called kara-nasubi."

[Miscellaneous Scroll II, upper row]

End of July

Kōzo (*Tororo-aoi* / Paper mulberry)

"Sketched the kōzo in the garden."

[Autumn Scroll, lower row, illustration 6]

Kanbun 9 (1669)

April 2

(Yama-odamaki / *Aquilegia buergeriana*)

"Received from Lord Abe of Bungo (Abe Tadaaki)"

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 10]

Kanbun 11 (1671)

May 27

Nuresagi (*Veratrum* / False hellebore)

"Received from Shibata Sanzaemon; called 'nuresagi'; said to be a rare flower."

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 9]

Kanbun 13 (1673)

January 16

(Plum)

"Drawn from life"

[Spring Scroll, lower row, illustration 1]

March 19

White Botan (white peony)

"Kishu-sama (Lord of Kii Province); white peony, 'uchinuki,' also called 'Keshimi.'"

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 31]

Enpō 2 (1674)

March 29

(Peony)

[Summer Scroll, lower row, illustration 33]

Plate 1: *Birds and Flowers of the Four Seasons*, owned by Eiheiji, 1635 (Kanei 12)